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GARBHINI PARICHARYA (ANTE-NATAL CARE) – VIEW OF HARITA SAMHITA (A TREATISE OF 10th CENTURY)

Shibani Dash^{1*}, Kamini Dhiman², Siba Prasad Rout³

^{1*}M.S. Scholar, Department of Stri Roga & Prasuti Tantra, All India Institute of Ayurveda, New Delhi- India- 110076,

²Associate Professor, Department of Stri Roga & Prasuti Tantra, All India Institute of Ayurveda, New Delhi-India-110076,

³M.D. Scholar, Department of Dravyaguna, I. P.G.T & R.A, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar.

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ABSTRACT

Woman, being the precious creation of the world is the only source for new creation. To procreate a healthy progeny is one of the esteem desire of a woman. Pregnancy although being a physiological phenomenon, still it may be at risk to face any complication at any stage due to the altered anatomical and physiological functions of the body of a pregnant female. To assure a safe motherhood as well as a healthy progeny in her womb, special care of a pregnant woman is required which is elucidated as antenatal care. In Ayurvedic classics, antenatal care has been given prime importance and elaborated as *garbhini paricharya* (antenatal care) by many *acharyas*. Basic objective of *garbhini paricharya* delineated in ayurveda is to achieve a healthy progeny of *srestha* (best) quality as well as to ensure a healthy mother or foetus during pregnancy, during labour and after labour. As per recent W.H.O report in 2000, it suggests that everyday approximately 830 die from preventable causes related to pregnancy and child birth. To reduce this rate, proper *garbhini paricharya* (ante-natal care) is the need of the day. *Acharya Harita* (a classical memory of 10th century) has given enormous emphasis upon *garbhini paricharya* and has documented special dietary as well as behavioural regimen in context to growth and development of foetus. *Yastimadhu* (*Glycchryza glabra* Linn.) acts as galactagogue whereas *Parusaka* (*Grewia asiatica* Roxb.) supplements iron, calcium to women body which she needs at correspondent stage. Vivid analysis of this recommended diet pattern of *Acharya Harita* suggests that he has charted out this scheduled diet pattern in a chronological order i. e. liquid to solid diet in order to prevent any complication arise during pregnancy and to provide a milieu interior to the body of mother as well as baby for better adapting power with the changing physiological phenomenon. Findings of this review article may validate the scientific validation of views of *Harita Samhita* recommended diet and habit for pregnancy.

Corresponding author

Kamini Dhiman

Associate Professor

Department of Stri Roga & Prasuti Tantra,

All India Institute of Ayurveda,

New Delhi, India- 110076,

kdaiaa@rediffmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the oldest system of medicine has laid enormous importance on safe motherhood. The aims and objectives of safe motherhood bestows upon the creation of healthy progeny with devoid of any anomalies following an easy delivery and safe guarding of health of mother, which, in other words termed as *garbhini paricharya*. It refers to the ante natal care including *ahara, vihara* for pregnant women for the benefit of both mother and foetus. Ancient scholars of Ayurveda have stated what to do and not to do for a pregnant women in detail, however *Acharya Harita* has prescribed a month wise dietary schedule in respect to growth and development of foetus too.[1] However, the scientific interpretation and validation of these points needs to be interpreted in today's era which is lacked, hence an attempt has been made in this manuscript to explore the month wise regimen for a pregnant woman described in *Harita Samhita* evidencing the scientific justification of this regimen.

Literature available in the library of AIIA, New Delhi pertaining to *Harita samhita*¹ and other ayurvedic classics [2-4], as well as Modern available literature texts have been scrutinized chapter by chapter by the authors. Information pertaining to recommended diet by *Acharya Harita* have been compiled meticulously and the compiled data have been equated with the views of other Ayurveda classics. Standard dictionaries were referred for the interpretation of classical ayurvedic terminologies for their probable English equivalent terms (William Monnier, A Sanskrit –English Dictionary, Oxford; 2007). Apart from these, various latest researches encompassing the evidence based claims were collected from various research journals and web based search engines like Google scholar, PubMed central, NCBI, Cochrane etc. and the details have been enumerated in respective contexts.

Sequential development *vis-a-vis* month wise recommended diet as per *Acharya Harita*

Ayurveda as well as modern parlance has thrown enough light upon the *Garbhavikasha* i.e sequential development of *Garbha* (embryo/foetus). Moreover, many classics of ayurveda have affirmed this developmental interpretation in month wise while observations of *Acharya Harita* to this concern was more accurate and distinct based on keenly observed changes transpired in couple of days or week in *Garbha* (embryo/foetus). To his opinion, the shape of *Garbha* (embryo/foetus) advances in chronological way like *budbud* (bubbles like); First day to *sonita* (resemblance of blood); tenth day then *Ghana* (solidified /compact); fifteenth day to *mamsapinda* (mass); twenty day etc. In order to provide proper nourishment and to fulfil the demands according to respective stages of *Garbha* (embryo/foetus), *Acharya Harita* has suggested to adopt a scheduled diet pattern as per month wise. The details of these diet pattern have been enumerated in Table-01 while the details of *Garbha vikasa krama* (sequence of development) has been presented in Table-02.

Table No. 1: Month wise recommended diet by *Acharya Harita*

Month	Recommended Diet
1 st	<i>Yastimadhu, parusaka, madhuka</i> with <i>Navaneeta, madhu, sarkara</i>
2 nd	<i>Kakoli-Sarkara-Dugdha</i>
3 rd	<i>Krishara</i>
4 th	<i>Samskruta Odana</i>
5 th	<i>Payasha</i>
6 th	<i>Madhura-Dadhi</i>
7 th	<i>Ghreeta khanda</i>
8 th	<i>Ghreeta Puraka</i>
9 th	<i>Vividhaanna</i>

Table No. 2: *Garbha vikasa krama* (sequence of development) according to *Harita Samhita*

Days / month	Development
First day	<i>Budbud</i> (Bubbles like)
Tenth day	<i>Sonita</i> (Resemblance of blood)
Fifteenth day	<i>Ghana</i> (Solidified/compact)
Twentieth day	<i>Mamsapinda</i> (fleshy mass)
Twenty fifth day	<i>Panchatwa prabhava</i> (five elemental things)
One month	<i>Panchabhuta</i>
Fifty day	<i>Ankura</i>
Three month	<i>Hasta, pada</i> (Parts and organs)
Three and half month	<i>Sira</i> (Head)
Fourth month	<i>Loma</i> (Lanugo hair)
Fifth month	<i>Sujiva</i> (lively)
Sixth month	<i>Sphurana</i> (quivering)
Eighth month	<i>Jatharagni</i> (Digestive fire)
Ninth month	<i>Chesta</i> (Organ systems able to function/activity)
Tenth month	<i>Prasava kala</i> (Onset of delivery)

DISCUSSION

First month

Acharya Charaka has mentioned that a pregnant woman should take non medicated milk in first month [2], *Acharya Sushruta* has advocated sweet, cold and liquid diet [3] and *Acharya Vagbhatta* in *Astanga Sangraha* has advised medicated milk [4]. *Acharya Harita* [5] has advised to consume *Madhuyashti*, *Madhukapuspa* with butter, honey and sweetened milk. *Yastimadhu* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) has been described in eleven *mahakashaya* by *Acharya Charaka* [6], also in both *chardi nigravana* (anti-emetics) & *vamanopaga* (adjuvants in emetic therapy) as it act as antiemetic in lower dose and emetic in a higher dose. *Parushaka* (*Grewia asiatica* Roxb.) is rich in iron, calcium, potassium, sodium & vitamin – C. [7]. It is useful in anaemia due to the presence of iron. *Madhuka* (*Madhuca indica*) contains albumin, saponin and act as a galactagogue [8-10]. Moreover, *yastimadhu* is a *sahayaka* drug (adjuvant) [11, 12]. So it act better with conjugating with other drugs. As a whole, *yastimadhu* combined with *parusaka / madhuka /* both of these with *navaneeta* (type of butter), *madhu* (honey), and *sarkara* (sugar) is given in order to relieve vomiting, dehydration, anaemia that arises in first month.

In the first month, *Acharya Harita* [13] has described the foetus to be formed as a *Ghana* from a liquid stage (*budbud*), so *madhura rasa* has been given which is comprised of *jala* and *prithvi mahabhuta* which may promote this solidification.

Second month

In the second month, *Acharya Charaka* has advocated milk medicated with drugs of *madhura rasa* [14]. *Acharya Sushruta* has prescribed sweet, cold and liquid diet to pregnant women [15]. *Acharya Vagbhatta* has advised milk medicated with *madhura dravyas* [16]. *Acharya Harita* [17] has been described sweetened milk treated with *Kakoli* (*Roscoca procera* Wall.) in second month of pregnancy. *Kakoli* (*Roscoca procera* Wall.) [18, 19] is a *jivaneeya dravya* (vitalizer) described both in *jeevaneeya mahakashya* [20-22] by *Acharya Charaka* & *jeevaneeya gana* by *Bhavprakashya*. As there is more chance of miscarriage in second month, so *jeevaneeya dravya* should be added to the diet of *garbhini*. It is also *valya* (tonic), *brihaniya* (nutrients), diuretic, *stanyajanana* (galactagogue) in actions.

Third month

In the third month of pregnancy, *Acharya Charaka* has advised milk with *madhu* and *ghrita*[23]. *Acharya Sushruta* has advocated the same sweet, cold and liquid diet to pregnant women [24]. *Acharya Vagbhatta* in *Astanga Sangraha* [25], has described milk with honey and *ghrita* in the third month of pregnancy. *Acharya Harita* [26] has prescribed *krishra* [27-29] (a special formulation of rice) to pregnant lady. *Krishra* (boiled and cooked gruel of different cereals) [30] acts upon excretory system as it is *malamutrakari* (repellent of faecal and urine). In addition to that, the formation of excretory system of foetus starts in third month.

In the third month, *Acharya Harita* [31] has described the formation of *hasta, pada and sira* in foetus. *Krishra*, being comprised of *guru guna* and *prithvi mahabhuta* may help in it.

Fourth month

In the fourth month of pregnancy, *Acharya Charaka* has advised milk with butter [32]. *Acharya Sushruta* has prescribed cooked *shasti* rice (*Oryza sativa* Linn.) with curd and pleasant food mixed with butter and meat of wild animals [33]. *Acharya Vagbhatta* in *Astanga Sangraha* has advised milk with one *tola* (12 gm) of butter [34]. *Acharya Harita* has been prescribed medicated cooked rice in the fourth month of pregnancy [35]. *Krutodana* (medicated cooked rice) comprises of carbohydrates which is the primary component for the growth of foetus in second trimester [36-38].

In fourth month, *Acharya Harita* has described the formation of *loma* in foetus. As there is description of *sthiraiva* in fourth month which is a *pitrujabhava*. [39]

Fifth month

In the fifth month, *Acharya Charak* has advocated *ghrita* prepared with butter extracted from milk [40]. *Acharya Sushruta* has advised cooked *sasthika* with milk, meat of wild animals along with dainty food mixed with milk and *ghrita* rice in the fifth month of pregnancy [41].

In *Astanga Sangraha*, *Acharya Vagbhatta* has advised *ghrita* prepared with butter extracted from milk [42]. *Acharya Harita* has emphasized on *payasa* in fifth month of pregnancy [43]. *Payasa* acts as *brihniya, valya* which is necessary in fifth month as the *garbhini* becomes *krisha* in this period as well as for the growth of foetus [44]. In fifth month, *Acharya Harita* [45] has described the foetus will be *sujiva* (lively).

Sixth month

In *Charaka Samhita*, *Acharya* has advised *Ghritha* prepared from milk medicated with *madhura* (sweet) drugs in sixth month of pregnancy [46]. In *Sushruta Samhita*, *Acharya* has advocated *Ghritha* or rice gruel medicated with *Gokshura* (*Tribulus terrestris* Linn.) [47]. In *Astanga Sangraha*, *Acharya* has described *Ghritha* prepared from Milk medicated with *madhura* (sweet) drugs in sixth month of pregnancy [48]. In *Harita Samhita*, *Acharya* has described sweetened curd in sixth month [49].

Curd is rich in vitamin- A, D, calcium, proteins, probiotics [50-51]. It cools down the body temperature & calms the emotional centre in order to prevent the anxiety. It also prevent the pigmentations i. e. *Kikissa* (*striae gravidarum*) that appears on sixth month.

In the sixth month, *Acharya Harita* has described that there will be *sphurana*(quivering) in foetus which may be sign of formation of locomotor and nervous system along with various reflex [52].

Seventh month

In *Charaka Samhita*, Acharya has emphasized on *ghrita* prepared from milk medicated with *madhura* (sweet) drugs in seventh month of pregnancy [53]. In *Sushruta Samhita*, Acharya has advised *ghrita* medicated with *prithakparnyadi* group of drugs [54]. In *Astanga sangraha*, Acharya has *ghrita* prepared from milk medicated with *madhura* (sweet) drugs in seventh month of pregnancy [55]. In *Harita Samhita*, Acharya has described *Ghritakhanda* (a sweet dish), *Ghritakhanada* [56-57] itself comprised of *ghrita* which contains good fats to create brown fat [58] in order to maintain the body temperature of foetus.

Eighth month

In *Charaka Samhita*, Acharya has described *yavagu* along with *dugdha* and *sarpi* in eighth month of pregnancy [59]. In *Sushruta Samhita*, Acharya has advocated *asthapana basti* (non-oily enema) [60]. In *Astanga Sangraha*, Acharya *vagbhatta* has advised *yavagu* along with *dugdha* and *sarpi* in eighth month of pregnancy [61]. In *Harita Samhita*, Acharya has advised *Ghritapuraka* to the pregnant women [62]. *Ghritapuraka* [63], also contain *ghrita* [64-65] which is required for the formation of *oja* as it become unstable in eighth month. So it is quiet essential in this time.

In the eighth month, Acharya *Harita* has described the formation of *jatharagni* (digestive fire) in foetus as a result of continuous ingestion of *ghritakhanda* and *ghritapuraka* [66].

Ninth month

In *Charaka Samhita*, Acharya has advised *Anuvasanabasti* (oily-enemata) with oil prepared with drugs of *Madhura* (sweet) group, vaginal tampon of this oil [67]. In *Sushruta Samhita*, Acharya has advised unctuous gruels and meat-soup of wild animals up to the period of delivery [68]. In *Astanga Sangraha*, Acharya has advocated *Anuvasanabasti* with oil prepared with drugs of *Madhura* (sweet) group, vaginal tampon of this oil [69]. In *Harita Samhita*, Acharya has advised *Vividhaanna* to pregnant women in the ninth month of pregnancy [70].

Different varieties of cereals [71] has been prescribed by Acharya *harita* as all the system has been completed and foetus is now able to take all type of *ahara* in order to maintain a balanced diet schedule. It also help to generate a wholesomeness of foetus.

In the ninth month, Acharya *Harita* has been described appearance of *chesta* in foetus which may be a sign of a fully formed foetus [72].

CONCLUSION

The period from conception to implantation is particularly important for foetal growth and development. Each stage of foetal development is dependent and influenced by appropriate maternal nutrient supply. Malnutrition, resulting from imbalances of macro and micronutrients before and during pregnancy, can negatively affect both mother and foetus as a whole, Acharya *Harita* has explained the diet of *garbhini* in order to prevent all the complications arises by the consequence of pregnancy. He has described in a chronological order i. e. first liquid, then semiliquid followed by semisolid, then solid diet so that the body of mother as well as baby can easily accommodate with the changing physiological phenomenon. Acharya *Harita* has also emphasized on the diet pattern of *garbhini* for the protection of both mother and child in particular. Epidemiological analysis and animal studies have shown that these nutritional influences early in life phase can influence the responsiveness of the body to the nutritional environment much later in life. The nutritional well-being of women as they conceive, affects not only the development of the foetus but also the genetic organization of the future metabolic responsiveness of the child and later, the adult. This area of epigenetics has become one of the fastest growing and most complex areas of biological science. (WHO – Good Maternal Nutrition the Best Start in Life– 2015). Recently AYUSH ministry has charted out prescription for pregnant woman in India which the experts and rationalists have termed as promotion of unscientific theories on pregnancy. The advisory disseminated by AYUSH ministry is based on the insights and views preached by ancient Ayurveda *Acharyas* from years and years ago, the present interpretation of this article may corroborate and enlighten the scientific background of this recommended diet advised by Acharya *Harita* in pregnancy and may propel as a future referencing.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors of this article doesn't have any conflict of interest.

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